

of the region are listed in the table. Dr. N. C. Pant, director, British Museum, London; and Dr. A. D. Pawar, assistant director (Biological Control), Directorate of Plant Protection Quarantine & Storage, assisted in the identification. ■

Table continued

Natural enemy	Host	Prevalence	Years of occurrence
<i>Aphidius</i> spp.	"	High	"
<i>Selina westermanni</i> (Mots.)	"	High	"
Spiders	"	High	"
<i>Amphipsyche meridiana</i> Ulmer	"	High	1975-76

Leaffolder outbreak in Kohima District, Nagaland, India

V. S. Pangtey and J. N. Sachan, ICAR Research Complex for NEH Region, Nagaland Centre, Medziphema 797106

Rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocis medinalis* Guenee was recorded as a minor pest in 1977 and 1978. But the pest caused heavy damage during the 1979 wet season (Jun-Nov), with infestations peaking in early September. Infestation

on IR8 leaves varied from 20% at higher altitudes (1,400 m mean sea level [MSL]) to 36% at lower altitudes (250 m MSL). Infestations seem to be increasing, up to 70% on IR8 and local variety Nagaland Special in 1981. ■

Gall midge incidence at Manipur, India

S. Amu Singh, District Agricultural Officer, Tengnoupal, Chandel, Imphal, Manipur, India

A heavy incidence of gall midge was recorded during 1979-80 kharif in a few pockets of Manipur. To assess the extent of pest incidence, a field survey was conducted in six subdivisions when the crop reached the mid- to late-tillering stage. Fifty hills per variety per loukol (a group of fields) was the survey unit. Observations were recorded from four survey units per subdivision. Varieties planted varied among subdivisions. Percentage of silver shoots was calculated on the basis of actual number of silver shoots and number of tillers per

Gall midge infestation in 6 subdivisions of Manipur, India.

Rice variety	Silver shoots (%)						Mean
	Imphal West 1	Imphal West 11	Imphal East	Thoubal	Bishenour	Churachandpur	
Punshi	22.0	12.7	32.4	23.8	15.0	—	21.2
Phouoibi	26.7	14.2	26.0	38.3	16.9	—	22.4
IR24	43.6	10.8	29.3	23.3	19.4	12.7	23.3
Ratna	46.4	—	6.9	23.2	—	24.5	25.2
P.33	42.1	9.8	—	5.6	21.0	—	19.6
Moirangphou	—	17.7	9.6	4.9	3.9	9.5	9.1
Phourel	—	—	6.2	5.1	6.5	11.27	7.2
Mean	36.2	13.0	18.4	17.8	13.8	14.7	18.3
CD (P = 0.05)	3.17	5.25	4.33	6.03	5.11	2.82	

unit.

Gall midge incidence (see table) was highest in Imphal West I and lowest in Imphal West II. The lowest use of plant protection in Imphal West I perhaps accounted for the high incidence of the pest there. In Churachandpur, gall

midge incidence was low because the area planted to susceptible high yielding varieties was small. Ratna, IR24, Punshi, and Phouoibi were found to be more susceptible to the insect than local varieties Phourel and Moirangphou (see table). ■

Occurrence of rice stem borers and gall midges at Tirur, Chingleput District, India

R. Saroja, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur 602025, India

To determine the damage patterns of yellow stem borer and gall midge, two major pests of rice in Chingleput, the susceptible variety IR8 was planted in 40-m² plots every month from July 1978 to June 1979. Recommended agronomic practices were adopted. The crop was given no insecticide treatment.

Stem borer and gall midge infestations were assessed at 60 days after transplanting by recording the number

Rice stem borer and gall midge damage to IR8 at Tirur, India, 1978-79.